

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING LISTENING SKILLS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6377069>

Matniyazova Nasiba Samandarovna

*Khorezm Academic Lyceum of the Ministry of
Internal Affairs in the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

English teacher.

Avezova Shaxlo Davronboyevna

*Khorezm Academic Lyceum of the Ministry of
Internal Affairs in the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

English teacher.

Annotation: *The article deals that the modern teaching with listening skills. Also, it is given the easy way improving languages listening skills below. The main purpose of the article is to find effective strategies that teachers can use to help ESL students improve their speaking skills and class participation.*

Keywords: *listening, improvement, strategies, pronounce, development, skills*

Language is a tool that we can use to communicate to each other. To communicate to the different country, we need global or international language. English is the one of global/ international language, which is used by all people around the world. Education is very important to improve yourself but learning English also improves the quality of life. Teaching speaking is a very important part of second language learning which are: Listening. Speaking. Essentially, speaking is very important in learning a language because as a social creature human need to interact one and another to express their ideas and thoughts to arrange and persuade others and it is used because someone purposes in learning a language is to be able to communicate the language.

Teaching listening skills is one of the most difficult tasks for any teacher of English as a foreign language. This is because successful listening skills are acquired over time and with a lot of practice. Effective, modern methods of teaching listening skills encompass everything from interactive exercises to multimedia resources. Listening skills are best learned through simple, engaging activities that focus more on the learning process than on the final product. Whether you are working with a large group of students or a small one, you can use any of the following examples to develop your own methods for teaching students how to listen well. Teaching listening can be done with various techniques, such as the use of a tape recorder, answering questions according to the text, rewriting songs, listening to television by watching video movie clips or CD -Rom, listening to the radio and using dictation, etc.

Principles for Good Listening:

1. Basics: Pay Attention. Even native speakers need help with this.
2. Practice Active Listening. Ask the speaker to slow down or repeat when you don't understand or just want to be certain about what you heard.
3. Pay Attention to Structure.

4. Listen for Key Words.

5. Key Phrases or Markers.

The improvement of listening skills depends on the level of development of students' phonological competence, which includes not only the correction of pronunciation of English sounds, but also the formation of listening skills, the correct use of their speech organs to reproduce sounds and intonation. The most difficult task is understanding a native English speaker.

Phonetic strategies: The student should listen carefully and pronounce words and sentences aloud. It must be remembered that words that are pronounced the same way may have different spellings and meanings (thread and through). Identical letters or letter combinations in words do not always give the same sound

Phonological strategies: It is important for the student to pronounce the words clearly and avoid phonological errors that distort the meaning of the utterance. (Are you fond of working here?/ Are you fond of walking here?/).

Listen and imitate individual sounds, pay attention to the pauses and intonation of the speaker. Practice "active listening", the ability to perceive and remember details of information. Due to the fact that the ability to listen effectively is an extremely important skill in teaching, each of us should take some time to assess how well we listen to our students. Think about the following principles:

The principles of effective listening are based on the knowledge and use of the factors that determine its effectiveness: attitude of listeners; listeners' interest; motivations of listeners; emotional state of listeners. The attitude of listeners: Effective listening requires an objective, open-minded, cooperative attitude of listeners.

Interests: People's interests can be primary, secondary and momentary. Primary interest exists when a person has a direct interest in what the speaker is talking about, when his ideas relate to everyday life. Secondary interests are universal interests concerning general issues of society (laws, programs, etc.)

Motivation: A person listens willingly when a speaker touches his basic desires and needs (money, increasing prestige, authority, preserving things dear to a person, etc.).

Emotional state. The speaker should understand that the audience listens better when it is free from emotional discomfort.

Tips for Teachers to Improve Their Public Speaking Skills: Know What You Want To Say. For good communication, you first need to clarify what exactly you want to say. Don't Be So Nervous. Relax. Make a Note of The Highlighted Point. Don't Memorize. Use Simple Words. Don't be Fast During Speaking. Use Sense of Humor. How do you promote speaking in the classroom?

Activities To Promote Speaking skills: Discussions. After a content-based lesson, a discussion can be held for various reasons. Role Play. One other way of getting students to speak is roleplaying; Simulations; Information Gap; Brainstorming; Storytelling; Interviews; Story Completion.

In addition, the teacher prompted the students to participate in the activities, and students' speaking is emphasized. Moreover, an activity involving competitive element where students work together can increase language productivity. The ability to

communicate in a second language clearly and efficiently contributes to the success of the learner in school and success later in every phase of life. Speaking skills are defined as the skills which allow us to communicate effectively. They give us the ability to convey information verbally and in a way that the listener can understand. Essentially, speaking a language helps to move your knowledge of grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation from the back of your mind to the front, or from your 'slow memory' to your 'quick memory'. Given time, this will improve their fluency and memory too. They revealed that the challenges they encountered most in teaching speaking are students' lack of vocabulary, pronunciation problems, nothing to say, lack of motivation and the use or interferences of the mother tongue. The reason why speaking is difficult aspect for students to master because they do not having enough exposure to English (environmental factor), infrequent English speaking practice in daily life (they could use the mother tongue to communicate, instead of using English), feeling shy and laziness to learn English. Many of students cannot speak clearly when they talk with foreigner because they don't know how to express what they want to say and how to say that. For it, they get a miss communication. To minimize the mistakes and get a good communication with native speakers or no, the learners must know and comprehend the use of expressions and the elements in speaking.

So, the classroom techniques is an interactive process of constructing meaning that involves producing, receiving and processing information. The achievements of good classroom techniques are when the people who interact understand each other and more easily to communicate well. Using game as the technique to teach speaking is the most interested way for the teacher and learners because it makes the learning processes in the classroom enjoyable. Using game also make the students happy not bored with classroom activity. The students can memorize the new vocabulary more easily. The technique also can develop their pronunciation.

Summing up, it should be noted that in order to form listening skills, it is necessary to use authentic material in the classroom that corresponds to the level of language proficiency of students, relevant to the topics studied and vocabulary. And also watching TV shows with the original English track will allow the student to train the skill of "passive listening", which will facilitate a smooth transition to the proactive use of listening. Repeating what you have heard one-on-one or the "parrot" technique is effective during passive listening. Such repetition involves facial expressions, makes it possible to listen to the sounds and rhythm of speech, allows you to practice listening and it is not necessary that the student understands everything in detail.

REFERENCES:

1. Brown, Douglas. H. 1994. Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy. United States of America: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
2. Richard, Jack C. 2001. Curriculum Development Language Teaching. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Parmawati, A. (2018). Using Analytic Teams Technique To Improve Students' speaking Skill.

3. Brown, G. & Yule, G. (1983). Teaching the spoken language, CUP Krashen, S.D. (1981). Second Language Acquisition and Second language learning, Pergamon Lynch, T. & Anderson, A. (1988).Listening, OUP.
4. Field, J. (2008). Listening in the language classroom, CUP Richards, J. C. (1990). The Language teaching matrix, CUP.